

ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE FORMATION OF A MOTIVATION SYSTEM THE PERSONNEL OF LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCIES

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Abstract: in this article, advanced foreign experience in the formation of a system of motivation for the activities of personnel of law enforcement agencies is studied, the structure of the professional motivation system has a multi-stage design, a number of proposals for improving this work are formulated in the power structures of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: motivation system, professional activity, serviceman, employee, law enforcement agencies, incentives, level, professional development, material incentives, career growth, service and combat tasks, service and labor activity.

At the present stage of development of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the reform involves the solution of a number of new tasks that determine not only the subsequent significant increase in the quality of equipment, weapons, but also the motivation for the service and labor activities of personnel, the targeted formation of motives for social responsibility, initiative, and creativity. There should be a significant increase in the composition of servicemen and employees who are motivated and able to carry out orders and tasks in conditions of social and informational uncertainty, capable of analytical self-assessment and self-management activity, ready to independently optimize the resource for completing the task, specify ways to implement it in a constantly updated, and sometimes aggressive environment, regardless of the danger to their own lives.

On January 13, 2022, an expanded meeting of the Security Council chaired by the Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev was held at the National Center for Defense Control of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 13, 2022, during the meeting, members of the Security Council, the command staff of the Armed Forces and the heads of the military administrative sectors were instructed, “Adopt a conceptual program for the development of the Armed Forces in 2022-2026 based on these goals and the nature of modern threats”, and as one of the priority tasks was determined: “In the current environment of increasing threats in the world In the information space, the urgency of ensuring information security, protecting young people from alien ideas, psychological training of military personnel and strengthening morale is growing, it was emphasized at the meeting” [1].

In order to implement the tasks set by the President, it is considered appropriate to revise the existing approaches to the psychological preparation of military personnel and employees both the Armed Forces in general and in law enforcement structures in particular, the improvement of methods and approaches to work on the formation of motivation for the activities of personnel, both in the performance of everyday service and combat missions, and in the performance of combat missions in the event of a military conflict.

Thus, in modern conditions, it is necessary not only to modernize the system of motivation for service and labor activity, but also the formation of mechanisms to stimulate service and labor activity, initiative practices of military personnel and employees. Therefore, the theoretical and practical study of the problems of motivation of service and labor activity of military personnel is relevant. and employees of law enforcement agencies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, development of new comprehensive principles of external motivation, clarification of general and its specific parameters.

In order to study the system of motivation for service activities of personnel of law enforcement structures, it is necessary to consider three fundamental terms:

A motive is a material or ideal object that induces and directs the activity or deed towards itself and for the sake of which it is carried out.

Combat motivation is a system of motives and incentives that determine and direct the combat activity of a warrior.

Will is a conscious organization and self-regulation by a person of his activity and behavior, aimed at overcoming difficulties in achieving the set goals; a special form of personality activity, a special type of organization of its behavior, determined by its own goal [2].

All actions of military personnel and employees in the course of performing service and combat missions are due to a certain averaged vector their motivation. There are no unmotivated actions, there is an unconscious personal motivation of a person. Without motivation, neither feat nor cowardice is possible.

It should be noted that the service and combat activities of military personnel and employees of law enforcement agencies have their own specifics, and, consequently, the corresponding (specific) motivation for achieving the set goal by representatives of law enforcement agencies.

In the course of reviewing the experience of specialists from the Russian Federation in the study of the system of motivation for the activities of personnel of law enforcement agencies, Ulybin S.V., in his scientific work "The dynamics of the development of military professional motivation among cadets of military institutions" defined the military professional motive (motivation) as a conscious need of the subject mediated by a specific goal, its reflection, manifestation in the military-professional self-determination of the individual [3].

This judgment is of great importance for improving the work on the formation of a system of motivation for the activities of the personnel of the power structures of the Republic of Uzbekistan, since it is the specifics of military professional motivation among cadets of military institutions is largely identical to the specifics of the professional motivation of the activities of law enforcement officers. V.A. Suvorov, revealing the essence of the professional motivation of officers of the internal troops, defines it as a system of professionally significant motives formed as a result of an officer's awareness of the social value of his work, determining the semantic component of his service and combat activity, realizing his capabilities in it through the fulfillment of assigned service and combat tasks, public recognition their achievements and the availability of an adequate system of incentives [4].

In the scientific work of Dodonov B.I., four structural motivational components are identified:

1. Pleasure from the activity itself;
2. Significance for the individual of its immediate result;
3. The "motivating" power of performance rewards
4. Coercive pressure on a person [5].

Today, Russian military experts are asking questions, what should be the non-material and material motivation for the military? How to turn service in the army from service to a privilege? A number of questions may be answered in the victorious end of the Special Military Operation in Ukraine and rallying Russian society in the interests of the victory of its army.

When considering the process of improving performance on the formation of a system of motivation for the activities of personnel of law enforcement agencies, it is impossible not to take into account the rich experience of the United States of America (hereinafter referred to as the United States).

In the US Armed Forces, there is a whole series of motives of a tangible and intangible nature. Difficult to measure they are quantitative and proportional, because the decision is quite individual and the weight of the arguments varies depending on the situation.

Material advantages for many, of course, serve as a convincing argument. The salary of contractors in the United States is not impressive in size. The salary for new recruits in the army is currently \$ 854, for junior officers - \$ 1636-\$ 3449, but it is stable, while in civilian life unemployment and competition in the labor market don't guarantee anything. When entering the service and when renewing the contract, a contract soldier is entitled to bonuses from \$20,000 for a soldier [6].

In the process of service, you can get a profession, and after two years of service, the army will pay for college education. Social Security and health insurance is valid not only during the service, but also for some time after it, which in America that does not burden itself with social obligations is a big plus. The military family will also receive material support. The wife will be helped to find a job at her husband's place of service, and the children will be helped to find a school.

Among the intangible factors, the motivating element is patriotism and the desire to serve the country.

Despite the fact that in America, as in Russia, the concept of patriotism has been discredited by politicians, serving the nation and American ideals remains a powerful driving force. The army is mainly replenished by people from the conservative American hinterland, where traditional values are not contested, unlike the cosmopolitan liberal coasts. Many Americans truly believe in America's mission to serve as an example of democracy and spread democratic values around the world.

The level of patriotism rapidly - regardless of geography - rises when there is a threat to the security and ideals of the country.

Admiration for one's army is another reason to apply to the service. It must be said that since the time of the development of the West, Americans have been passionate about military affairs, and American militarism has very deep and powerful roots. There is another important point: in the American - as, indeed, any other - modern society, where there are no standards of masculinity, only the army is able to offer the ideal of a man.

The army is still attractive for its traditional values, which are the same for many cultures and have changed little over the centuries: belonging to a special group of people

guided by high principles, true male friendship, solidarity and mutual assistance, military romance, the desire to do something meaningful in life, to serve a noble purpose, to get away from banality, philistinism and mediocrity. The army allows you to become a real man.

Having served in the army, there is no longer any need to prove or justify something. The career military is completely supported by the state, and after his resignation he is guaranteed a decent life.

Their salaries are lower than what they could earn, *ceteris paribus*, in the private sector, but a military career is not made for material rewards. Business gives money; politics gives power; a military career brings respect. The prestige of military service is crystallized in the US Marine Corps. Special units have a reputation as elite units: the United States, France, Israel, Great Britain, but the most striking and generally recognized example of an elite formation is the US Marine Corps. Material rewards and higher education, the Marine Corps promises nothing. Instead of promises, she asks:

"Will you pull?" The material reward in the marines is less than in other troops. The highest honor she can offer is the right to call herself a Marine. Once deserving this title, a person remains a marine for life: there are no former marines. The Marine Corps is more than a corporation.

This is a brotherhood. "I" becomes "we"; Marines work as a team and are ready to sacrifice themselves to an idea. Their motto is "Honor, Courage, Duty". The marine, with all the most modern military equipment, remains a warrior, as warriors were two millennia ago. All Marines, no matter what functions they perform, first of all, fighters and shooters and can join the battle instantly. All without exception pass the same standardized basic training that creates a sense of unity and corporateness. Knowledge of the history of the Marine Corps, the most important battles, spirit and ethos strengthens unity, asserts exclusivity and prestige [6].

According to the American sociologist and political scientist Samuel Phillips Huntington, a military professional must meet three main criteria:

First, experience.

A professional is an expert who has a set of special knowledge and skills in an important area of human activity. In military affairs, professionalism, in addition to highly specialized knowledge and skills, requires an understanding of the general cultural tradition of society. Therefore, training for a profession should consist of two phases: a broad humanitarian base and specialized knowledge. The peculiarity of the competence of the military profession is the possession of one unique skill, which is not found in civilian professions. This is the ability to manage force (management of violence; the concept was introduced by the sociologist Harold Lasswell). The ability to control force appears in the process of forming an officer; it is not given by memorizing any methods. A conscript, unlike a professional, learns to use force (application of violence).

The second criterion of military professionalism is responsibility.

A professional is an expert who practices his craft in a certain social context, providing a service to society as a whole and to each of its members in particular. Responsibility is a key concept for professions providing public services. If, for example, a doctor who took the Hippocratic oath, instead of treating patients, begins to harm their health, he ceases to serve society. In the case of an officer, the very fact of possessing a special ability to control power gives him responsibility and obliges him to use this skill. for the benefit of society.

Third, corporatism.

An officer is a state corps, with its own strict hierarchy and delineation of tasks, the entrance to which is available only to holders of special knowledge and skills. Membership in the officer corps gives the legal right to practice the military profession. The officer works and lives separately from society; the circle of his "personal" contacts mainly includes, again, colleagues in the profession. Members of the officer corps are organically united and are aware of their group as a special group in society; belonging it is created by long-term preparation, discipline and awareness of social responsibility [7].

Thus, having considered the advanced Russian and American experience in the formation of a system of motivation for the activities of personnel of law enforcement agencies, in order to improve the process of motivating military personnel and employees of law enforcement agencies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is advisable to adapt the considered experience and reform the existing system of motivation for representatives of law enforcement agencies.

Taking into account the content of various approaches to the interpretation of the structure of the motivation system, the specifics of the development of the personality of a serviceman, an employee at various stages of professional development, it can be assumed that the structure of the professional motivation system has a multi-stage structure and can consist of the following main interrelated levels:

1. Becoming in office, at this level, a serviceman, an employee of the power structure learns the features of service and combat tasks assigned to the power structure, assigned functional duties based on the position held, traditions and rituals specific to this structure, the requirements of working time regulations and work ethics of conduct, as well as a system of moral and material incentives and guarantees legally enshrined in this structure at the state level. In turn, it should be noted that potential candidates for the service have a wide range of different value orientations: from pronounced consumer and selfish, to the presence of bearers of the ideals of selfless service to the Motherland and the readiness of personal participation in ensuring national security.

For this reason, a necessary requirement is the creation of the necessary conditions for the high-quality professional selection of candidates for this structure, with the determination of the true motives of candidates when applying for a job and the qualities and abilities that are in demand for this structure and a certain specialty.

This level is completed on the basis of the results of working out a plan for the commissioning of a serviceman, an employee.

2. Professional development, at the second level, a serviceman, an employee of the power structure "hones" his professional knowledge, skills and abilities, intensively applying them in the course of his service and combat activities, strives to increase career growth. The main motive at this level is the need for promotion and taking a more status position in the team. and society. This level moves to a higher stage, provided that a serviceman, an employee of a specialty, achieves such a level of development, when he, in the course of working in his position in the course of performing the assigned service and combat tasks, is capable of reasonable initiative, creativity, independence in choosing the most effective methods and means achieving the goal.

3. Professional excellence, upon reaching this level, motivation reaches its peak when a soldier, an employee along with with the constant improvement of his professional level

(passing advanced training courses, studying at the Academy, University, defending an academic degree, obtaining an academic title) transfers personal experience and knowledge to other military personnel, employees. It should be emphasized that the most important motivational result of the professional development of a serviceman, an employee of law enforcement agencies as a highly qualified specialist in his position is his ability, along with his direct professional activity, to be an educator and mentor.

As an improvement in the work on the formation of a system of motivation for the activities of the personnel of the power structures of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the best foreign experience, a number of proposals can be identified.

In the power structures of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I consider it expedient to create the necessary conditions for:

- ensuring organizational conditions and opportunities for active labor initiatives based on the abilities of military personnel and employees;
- modernization of the norms of service and labor interaction, expansion of the scope and possibilities for the manifestation of professional reasonable initiative;
- increasing the effectiveness of material factors motivating the real labor activity of military personnel, employees of law enforcement agencies of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- formation of an open system of social assessment of the labor activity of servicemen and employees.

All the studies conducted in the article allow us to conclude that the improvement of work on the formation of a motivation system to the activities of the personnel of law enforcement agencies becomes a significant creative force in the system of ensuring the combat capability of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and her experience is worthy of careful and comprehensive study and implementation.

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